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Practice of workforce flexibility - internal, external, numerical and functional flexibility

Abstract

There is a considerable absence of research literature that evaluated ways in which people management practices such as workforce flexibility operate in different contexts. The purpose of the study is to investigate four workforce flexibility strategies used in export-based firms. These four strategies are external flexibility, internal flexibility, functional flexibility and numerical flexibility. To fulfil the objectives of the study, the paper presents results of four surveys conducted to investigate each of the flexibility strategy in Sri Lanka. Two of these surveys were conducted in the service sector of off-shore IT outsourcing while the other two were conducted in the export-based manufacturing sectors of coir product manufacture and apparel manufacture. In another dimension, two studies were on executive and above level employees while the other two were on shop-floor employees.

Keywords: Flexible work hours, employment status, shift-work, job rotation, horizontal and vertical skill integration, casual workers, permanent workers, shop-floor workers.

Introduction

There have been new theories, technologies and practices replacing old ones. An example of the changing realities of work is workforce flexibility. The use of workforce flexibility or flexible forms of work scheduling is on the increase (Twinaime, Humphries, & Kearins, 2006; Beers, 2010). Although workforce flexibility can be identified as a strategy to address changing requirements of external and internal organizational environment (Twinaime et al., 2006), it brings previously uncharted challenges for both employers and employees. Workforce flexibility strategies are expected to create a working relationship, which simultaneously recognises and realises the needs of organizations and individuals. Therefore, workforce flexibility demands new forms of work organization and management. At the same time, it brings individuals and organizations benefits that cannot be ignored (Beers, 2010). In

this context, organizations need to have a vision of future workplaces and future workers in order to manage the necessary structural, technological and psychological changes involved in adopting workforce flexibility strategies.

People or human resource is the most important resource that controls the other two resources of capital and technology which involved in economic activities. Organizations can adopt different forms of workforce flexibility strategies to maximize the potential and contribution of human resources to the organization (Fullick et al., 2009). As reviewed in detail in the next section, these strategies are identified as external flexibility, internal flexibility, functional flexibility and numerical flexibility. This paper presents results of four separate empirical studies that investigated each strategy, namely, flexible work hour arrangement (internal flexibility), permanent vs casual employment status (external flexibility), shift-work (numerical flexibility), and job rotation and horizontal and vertical skill integration (functional flexibility). As reviewed in the next section, each of these strategies allows organizations to maximize on differences in human potential in terms of experience, qualifications, interests, skills and abilities at the same time allowing employees to attain their personal needs (e.g. family responsibilities).

Although organizations have adopted different strategies to address the changing needs of a diversified workforce, a few research publications exist on workforce flexibility strategies. The main shortcoming of these publications lays, on the one hand, that they presented a limited number of strategies in a single study (e.g. Beers, 2010). Therefore, it is reasonable to present these strategies, which are until recently had been studied separately, in a single publication. Second, changes occurred with the globalization of business operations and increase in operating costs in the West increased the importance of developing countries in manufacturing and export trade. Still, developing countries have to maintain their locations as effective as possible to maintain attractiveness as a global business hub. Therefore, considering the interest in understanding strategies that can be used to make work contexts effective, it is of importance to understand ways in which workforce flexibility strategies are adopted by export-based industries. In the above context, the main objective of this paper is to present ways in which workforce flexibility strategies are used by export-based industries in Sri Lanka. The specific objectives in relation to the four studies were:

1) Study 1 - Internal flexibility (flexible work hour arrangement):

To investigate employees' evaluation of flexible work hour arrangement; employees' views of attractiveness of flexible work hour arrangement in attracting

and retaining employees; and employers' evaluation of flexible work hour arrangement in terms of operational efficiency.

2) Study 2 - External flexibility (permanent vs casual employment status):

To investigate whether permanent workers and casual workers exhibit different work-related attitudes.

3) Study 3 - Numerical flexibility (shift-work):

To investigate employees' evaluation of shift-work; and whether their evaluation varies by age and marital status.

4) Study 4 - Functional flexibility (job rotation and horizontal and vertical skill integration):

To investigate whether employees experience autonomy support, social support and competence support at work; and whether these experiences lead to a higher level of job performance in lean production.

Consistent with the objectives, the rest of the article reviews available literature on workforce flexibility. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Review of literature

Workforce flexibility strategies

There are four workforce flexibility strategies, namely, external flexibility, internal flexibility, functional or qualitative flexibility and numerical or quantitative flexibility (Looise, van Riemsdijk, & Lange, 1998). Of these, internal flexibility involves managing fluctuations and/or changes in the labour demand by using the existing workforce at the workplace (e.g., flexible working hours and overtime). External flexibility involves the use of labour from external labour market when necessary (e.g., the use of temporary contracts). Numerical flexibility involves making variations to the amount of work performed by employees (e.g., changing the number of work hours through shift-work). Functional flexibility involves making variations to the content of work with regard to workers' qualifications (e.g., job rotation and horizontal and vertical skill integration) (Looise et al., 1998).

Workforce flexibility strategies aim to address changing environmental requirements as a part of firms' strategic approach towards people management (Standing, 2008). At the

national level, workforce flexibility strategies help to mitigate unemployment, promote competitiveness, and thereby enhance economic performance. Therefore, these strategies have the potential to promote societal outcomes of re-distribution of work between the employed and unemployed. At the firm level, workforce flexibility strategies help to make changes to the composition of workforce as a way of recruitment and retention of people. The use of flexibility strategies have increased during the recent past and expected to remain popular in the years to come (Twina et al., 2006).

However, previous research provided evidence that employees felt more stressed, reported greater dissatisfaction for flexibility arrangements, and felt less satisfied with the nature of communication and consultation occurred prior to the introduction of these strategies (Haines, Marchand, Rousseau, & Demers, 2008). These issues raise concerns about the role of human resource function in managing employees' expectations and experience in the workplace. Therefore, it is important to understand employees' reactions to workforce flexibility strategies. Such an understanding could provide valuable information for strategic decision-making allowing suitable updates to be made to prevent the deterioration of workplace conditions.

Internal flexibility - flexible work hour arrangement

The traditional fixed times that full-time employees start and finish the working day are replaced in flexible work hour arrangement with some freedom for employees to choose their daily start and end times (Wickramasinghe & Wickramanayake, 2013). Although there are variations in its form, the basic model of flexible work hour arrangement usually consists of five interrelated components: (a) a bandwidth within which all hours must be worked, (b) a core time during which all employees are required to be working, (c) a flexible band of hours before, after, or in between core times that allows employees to exercise designated options regarding their presence in, or absence from the work place, (d) banking, which allows carry-over of surplus or deficient hours worked, and (e) variability of schedule- employees' freedom to vary working hours from one period to another without prior approval from their supervisor. These five components of flexible work hour arrangement determine the extent of flexibility permitted to employees. Flexible work hour arrangement may be in operation as a part of human resource benefit package offered to employees; it can be adopted in professional, managerial or operational settings (Almer & Single, 2004; Wickramasinghe & Chandrasekara, 2011; Wickramasinghe & Wickramanayake, 2013).

In response to the offering of flexible work hour arrangement, employees' overall positive feeling toward the employer increases, which may reciprocate with greater organizational commitment, reduced levels of stress and increased job satisfaction (Wickramasinghe & Jayabandu, 2007). Such positive attitudes are created due to several reasons. First, employees may perceive that the organization's offering of flexible work hour arrangement as representing its concern for providing work patterns which facilitate them to combine work and personal life. Second, an individual often engages in social comparison process and may compare his/her situation to peers in other organizations that do not offer flexible work hour arrangement. Such comparisons could increase the value of psychological contract with the organization. Third, flexible work hour arrangement can provide a context for a more efficient utilization of the human 24 hour clock. This can decrease the amount of stress, i.e., work arrival related stress and stress over work and non-work time demands experienced by some employees (Haines et al., 2008). Women would be more likely to report higher levels of organizational commitment, retention and job satisfaction than men when they perceive that a family-responsive policy is present in their organization than when it is not (Wickramasinghe & Jayabandu, 2007). Further, organizations with flexible work hour arrangement are more attractive to job seekers than those with a standard work arrangement. It is also suggested that when employees become conditioned to flexible work hour arrangement, they are less likely to join some other organization where such a system is not available (Rau & Hyland, 2002). All these may contribute to workplace adjustment by permitting an increased alignment between an employee's abilities and the ability requirements of the job.

Overall, building on the above reviewed literature, as a people management practice, flexible work hour arrangement provides considerable benefits to both employers and employees, where employees developing work patterns which facilitate them to combine work and personal-life commitments while organizations experiencing increased attraction rates and lower employee turnover rates. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H1: Employees' evaluation of flexible work hour arrangement varies by their sex and marital status. It is expected that females and married employees may have more positive evaluation compared to males and single employees.

External flexibility - permanent vs casual employment status

Employment status (permanent vs casual) is a main criterion of the exchange relationship between the employing organization and its people. Permanent employment arrangement

involves the “standard” model of year-round full-time employment with statutory benefits, opportunities for training and advancement as well as job security (Louie et al., 2006). Outside this arrangement lays non-standard employment arrangements that involve seasonal, casual, fixed-term, probationary, and an apprentice. The current study is confined to casual employment arrangement. Casual employment is identified as an unprotected form of employment with the absence of many standard benefits, rights and forms of protection compared to permanent employment (MacPhail & Bowles, 2008; Standing, 2008).

However, it is identified, on the one hand, that casual workers are employed at the same organization for a longer period of tenure. Pocock, Buchanan and Campbell, (2004) and Louie et al. (2006) identified this as “permanent casuals” where casual workers were assigned to perform regular jobs with longer periods of tenure. On the other hand, casual workers are made to perform core functions, which are more vital than that of peripheral functions. In general, it is expected that core job functions to be performed by permanent workers where as peripheral functions to be performed by those (such as casuals) who are loosely connected to the organization (Olsen, 2006). If permanent workers are performing tasks along with casual workers who also engaged in core tasks, the identification of them as inferior to permanent workers become problematic. Second, this situation reflects a desire on behalf of management to increase the alignment of labour resources to the needs of the organization rather than treating employees with equal or fair opportunity commitments (Twinaime et al., 2006). Third, this situation implies a growing inferior jobs and irregular labour force in the labour market (Saloniemi & Zeytinoglu, 2007).

In the above context, there is a rationale for us to propose that the two groups of workers could depict differences in their perceptions due to the characteristics of exchange relationship (MacPhail & Bowles, 2008; Wickramasinghe & Chandrasekara, 2011). Specifically, casuals could have poorer attitudes and may exhibit poorer work outcomes; they do not become embroiled in the organization’s culture (Standing, 2008; Wickramasinghe & Chandrasekara, 2011). Therefore, we propose that the work-related attitudes of job satisfaction, job performance, turnover intention, absenteeism and opportunities for skill development could be different between permanent workers and casuals. It is hypothesized:

H2: Work-related attitudes vary by employment status where casuals depict poorer work-related outcomes than that of permanent workers.

Numerical flexibility – Shift-work

Shift-work allows firms to make variations in the amount of work. In a shift-based work schedule employees succeed each other at the same workstation in shifts that range from 17- or 24-hour time span on some regular basis from daytime to evening or night-time as directed by the firm (Beers, 2010). Organizations that use several shifts to cover a particular working day can organize shift schedules in a rotating pattern, where rosters frequently change between day, evening and night. Alternatively, organizations can use fixed shift schedules, where working hours and working days do not rotate from week to week (Fullick et al., 2009). Hence, shift-work schedules may differ markedly in terms of organization, timing and the duration of each shift as well as the speed of rotation of shifts.

Whilst there are benefits of shift-work, it has also been associated with several negative effects on employees in comparison to traditional working day. Some studies showed that shift-work facilitates effective allocation of employees to specific shifts and financial benefits such as increased income (King & Torkzadeh, 2008; Sakthivel, 2007). However, some other studies showed that shift-work associates with some costs and risks (Haines et al., 2008; Wickramasinghe & De Silva, 2011). Little as one night of sleep deprivation impairs complex tasks such as decision-making, ability to control one's emotions and decreased motivation (e.g., Haines et al., 2008; Wickramasinghe & De Silva, 2011). Shift-workers also find difficulties in maintaining performance levels since shift-work influences their speed, reaction time, and the accuracy of work performance after the evening hours begin, and this situation is particularly true for rotating shift-workers (Burgess, 2007). Several episodes of sleep loss can create a sleep debt which can have noticeable effects on work performance. On the contrary, Finn (1981, p. 32) observed that many shift-workers have less tension and more relaxed pace on the night shift than during the day because of less supervision and fewer interruptions from clerical and management personnel. Further, shift-work can be advantageous to a family's financial situation as it brings increased wages (Fullick et al., 2009). Overall, these findings call for improvements in the areas that are deleterious while retaining or enhancing those that are beneficial to help the industries to flourish at large. Based on the literature reviewed above, it is hypothesized for the study:

H3: Employees' evaluation of shift-work varies by age and marital status. It is expected that younger and single employees may have more positive evaluation compared to older and married employees.

Functional flexibility - job rotation and horizontal and vertical skill integration

Firms can make changes to the content of work with regard to the qualification of workers by designing jobs involving job rotation and horizontal and vertical skill integration. In the manufacturing context, functional flexibility by way of job rotation and horizontal and vertical skill integration creates more competent and reliable behaviour. It leads to greater levels of trust based on the expectation that others will behave in a helpful manner that is reliable and predictable in performing job duties (Evans & Davis, 2005). Overall, this strategy facilitates the institutionalisation and maintenance of organizational change processes, such as the implementation of lean production.

Work design in lean production demands shop-floor employees to perform multiple tasks, rotate between tasks, self-regulate the work speed, make process improvements and monitor the quality of products by themselves. When numerical flexibility becomes inappropriate due to quality requirements, customisation, continuous innovation and product differentiation, firms have to rely on functional flexibility to assign workers to tasks at a minimum cost (Karlsson & Åhlström, 1995). Functional flexibility allows to assign employees in a number of potential alternative tasks to which individuals' skills can be applied (resource flexibility), and to make decisions on how individuals with different skills can be quickly redeployed (coordination flexibility).

Job design plays a greater role in achieving functional flexibility in lean production by assigning employees to work in different capacities with diverse tasks on a day-to-day basis (McDonald, Ellis, Van Akenand, & Koelling, 2009). This demands workers to be rotated on job tasks and the provision of training in multi-skills. Multi-skilling through training increases the flexibility to meet fluctuating demand, create a shared sense of responsibility and balance the workload between workers. In other words, training provides resource flexibility in terms of employees' skills and behaviours. Specifically, when a group of shop-floor workers are trained on consecutive tasks, whether upstream or downstream, they can apply a variety of skills and talents in a number of potential alternative uses and work in different capacities (Wickramasinghe & Wickramasinghe, 2016). Overall, functional flexibility allows employees to become more self-managing with horizontal and vertical coordination. As a result, they could enjoy task variety, immediate feedback on their own performance, the self-regulation of work speed, the shared sense of responsibility, balanced workload between workers, and social interaction and co-operation among them (McDonald et al. 2009; Wickramasinghe & Wickramasinghe, 2016). In the above context, we propose

that shop-floor workers in lean production may experience competence supportive, autonomy and initiative supportive, and social supportive workplace. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H4: Autonomy support, social support and competence support at work have significant positive effects on job performance.

Method

Study 1: Internal flexibility

Population and sample. The study was confined to full-time employees engaged in off-shore software development firms. For the study, an employee is described as “a person involved in producing IT related output as his/her primary job function”. We identified 15 firms that had adopted formal flexible work hour arrangement for employees, who come under above definition. When considering the ownership of companies, 4 were locally owned, 7 were joint ventures and 4 were foreign owned. Although there were slight variations in flexible work hour arrangements, the existence of core work hours and a bandwidth, and the implementation of this arrangement to job positions that were judged feasible were found to be common across the firms as described in Wickramasinghe and Jayabandu (2007).

A total of 108 valid responses were yielded for the self-administered questionnaire. Of the respondents, 65% were male and 35% were female. Sixty two percent were single and 38% were married. With regard to the highest level of education, 26% had postgraduate degrees, 63% had Bachelor's degrees, and the remaining had diploma level qualifications. The average age was 32 years. The mean tenure in the present firm was three and half years. As the study intends to explore whether flexible work hour arrangement had improved the operational efficiency, in the second stage, information was obtained from the person in charge of operations of the firms using a short questionnaire.

Measures and methods of data analysis. The features of flexible work hour arrangement were measured by the 13-item scale developed for the study. Items are shown in Table 1. Factor analysis produced five factors as shown in Table 2. The operational efficiency is defined as “the extent to which firms achieved project targets and the extent to which employees covered the expected number of hours for the scheduled period”. All the measures were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree). Data screening was conducted following the guidelines recommended by Hair et al. (2006). Descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test and logistic regression were used for the data

analysis. For the logistic regression, sex (female = 0, male = 1) and marital status (single = 0, married = 1) were binary coded. Data were analysed using SPSS software package.

Study 2: External flexibility

Population and sample. The study was confined to a single organization, where casual workers engaged in core job functions with lengthy periods of tenure along with workers in permanent job positions in the shop-floor. The selected organization was one of the main exporters of synthetic fibre products in Sri Lanka. The total number of employees engaged in the firm was 246 of which 12 were belonging to managerial-level, 32 were belonging to administrative categories and 202 were belonging to shop-floor operator categories. Of the 202 shop-floor operators, 92 were identified as permanent where as 110 were identified as casuals in the organization records. All permanent and casual shop-floor workers were categorized either as skilled or semi-skilled. Casual workers were paid wages on a weekly basis. Employees of this organization were not unionized as described in Wickramasinghe and Chandrasekara (2011). An identical self-administered survey questionnaire was used to collect data from both groups of workers. From each group, 40 voluntarily completed questionnaires were received resulting in 43 percent response rate from permanent workers and 36 percent response rate from casual workers.

Of the permanent workers, 83% were male and 17% were female. The average age was 34 years (SD = 10). Twenty seven percent were single and 73% were married. With regard to the highest level of education, 10% had less than ten years of schooling, 83% had ten years of schooling, and 7% had 12 years of schooling. The mean tenure in the current workplace was nine years (SD = 7); the mean tenure in the industry was 12 years (SD = 8). Of the casual workers, 68% were male and 32% were female. The average age was 31 years (SD = 11). Fifty percent were single and 50% were married. With regard to the highest level of education, 32% had less than ten years of schooling, 63% had ten years of schooling, and 5% had 12 years of schooling. The mean tenure in the current workplace was four years (SD = 2); the mean tenure in the industry was seven years (SD = 5).

Measures and methods of data analysis. Five work-related attitudes were investigated. These were job satisfaction, job performance, absenteeism, intention to stay, and opportunities for skill development. The 2-item scale from Thatcher, Stepina, and Boyle, (2002) was used to measure job satisfaction. These items are “Generally speaking, I am very satisfied with this job” and “I am generally satisfied with the kind of work I do”. Factor analysis produced a

single factor. The 5-item self-rating scale developed by Rodwell, Kienzle, and Shadur (1998) was used to measure job performance. Example items are “I am currently working at my best performance level” and “I am proud of my work performance”. Factor analysis produced a single factor. Absenteeism was measured by a single item developed for the study, i.e., “I get absent because of I am not interested in my job”. Intention to stay was measured by a single item from Kim, Price, Mueller and Watson, (1996), i.e., “I plan to stay with my present employer as long as possible”. Opportunities for skill development were measured by the three items from Tremblay, Guay and Simard (2000). Example items are “Several professional development activities are offered to employees to improve their skills and knowledge”, and “Managers encourage employees to apply their abilities and skills in the context of their daily work”. Factor analysis produced a single factor. All the measures were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree). As detailed above, factor analysis was conducted (principal components with Varimax rotation) for all measurement scales. Descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test and logistic regression were used for the data analysis. For the logistic regression, the status of employment was binary coded (casual = 0, permanent = 1). Data were analysed using SPSS software package.

Study 3: Numerical flexibility

Population and sample. The study was confined to employees full-time engaged in off-shore software development firms that provide services on shift-basis located in the country. For the study, an employee is described as “a person who is engaged in the creation and provision of IT-related output as his or her primary job function on shift-basis”. The preliminary investigations made by the authors led to identify eight firms that use shift-based work pattern covering the full working hours of a particular working day. A detailed description of shift work characteristics of these firms can be found in Wickramasinghe and De Silva (2011).

There were a total of 303 IT professionals engaged full-time on shift-based work pattern in these eight firms. A total of 133 usable responses resulted in 44% response rate. Of the respondents, 90% were male and 10% were female. Forty seven percent were single and 53% were married. With regard to the highest level of education, 34% had postgraduate degrees, 56% had Bachelor’s degrees, and the remaining 10% had diploma level qualifications. The average age was 30 years. The mean tenure as a shift-worker was four years.

Measures and methods of data analysis. The information on the characteristics of shift-work was obtained in relation to working hours, shift-work structure and the nature of shift rotation. Employees' evaluation of shift-work was measured by the 13 items developed for the study as shown in Table 5. The items were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree). As detailed above, factor analysis was conducted (principal components with Varimax rotation) for all measurement scales. Descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test and logistic regression were used for the data analysis. For the logistic regression, age (less than 35 years = 0, more than 35 years = 1) and marital status (single = 0, married = 1) were binary coded. Data were analysed using SPSS software package.

Study 4: Functional flexibility

Population and sample. The study was confined to shop-floor employees who were full-time engaged in lean production implemented export-based textile and apparel manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. Since mid-2000s, these firms are changing their production methods and management practices to become leaner and fitter to improve the efficiency of production systems. We identified 14 firms that had implemented lean production systems and that had achieved considerable progress in the implementation of lean production systems as described in Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe (2016).

For the study, a random sample of 670 shop-floor operators from these firms responded. In total, 25% were males while 75% were females. The average age was 28 years. With regard to the highest level of education, 58% had 10 years of schooling while 42% had 13 years of schooling. The average number of shop-floor workers in a team/section was 56. The average years of experience in the job position was four years and the average years of experience with the present employer was three years and three months.

Measures and methods of data analysis. Autonomy support was measured by the three items from Bauer and Mulder (2006). Example items are "I can try out new things in my job" and "I can participate in decisions concerning my resources for work". Factor analysis produced a single factor. Social support was measured by the five items from Bauer and Mulder (2006). Example items are "If I experience difficulties at work, I receive support from my colleagues" and "We stick together in our department". Factor analysis produced a single factor. Competence support was measured by the three items from Bauer and Mulder (2006).

Example items are “I have the possibility to gain new knowledge and skills in my work” and “I can actually use my competences in my work”. Factor analysis produced a single factor. As described in Study 2, Rodwell et al.’s (1998) 5-item self-rating scale was used to measure job performance. All the measures were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree). As detailed above, factor analysis was conducted (principal components with Varimax rotation) for all measurement scales. Correlation and regression analysis were used to test the hypothesised relationships. Data were analysed using SPSS software package.

Results and discussion

Study 1: Internal flexibility

The results of employees’ evaluation of flexible work hour arrangement are shown in Table 1. Items marked with (R) were reverse-scored; higher scores indicate favourable attitudes towards the use of flexible work hour arrangement. The mean values shown in Table 1 indicate a positive evaluation of the arrangement. There were significant differences between males and females for three items, namely, “leads to difficulties in interacting with colleagues” (R) ($p < 0.01$), “feels disconnected from workplace” (R) ($p < 0.05$) and “provides time for higher studies” ($p < 0.05$). Females scored higher values for all these items with compared to males. However, only one item showed significant differences by marital status, i.e., “provides time for higher studies”, where single employees scored higher mean values compared to married employees (single: mean = 3.50, SD = 0.89; married: mean = 2.90, SD = 0.91; $t = 2.361$; $p < 0.01$).

Take in Table 1

Factor analysis yielded five factors as shown in Table 2. We identified these factors as “relations with others at work”, “effects on life at work”, “balancing work-life”, “feeling of freedom”, and “attention to work”. The analysis of these broad categories did not reveal any significant differences by sex or marital status.

Take in Table 2

Table 3 shows the results of logistic regression. For this, the significant items from Table 1 were used. Hosmer and Lemeshow test yielded p-value of 0.72 suggesting a good fit. Further, the overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 73. It is evident from Table 3 that these three items differentiate employees by sex. The odds of females to perceive less difficulty in interacting with colleagues (as opposed to males) are 3.97 times as high. The odds of females to perceive more free time for higher studies (as opposed to males) are 0.98 times as high. The odds of females to perceive less disconnected from workplace (as opposed to males) are 0.5 times as high.

Take in Table 3

Independent sample t-test was conducted to identify any significant differences regarding the attractiveness of flexible work hour arrangement for the attraction and retention of employees by sex and marital status. The two items used for this were “Reluctance to change the current employer because of flexible work hour arrangement” and “Consider flexible work hour arrangement as important in future workplaces”. For both items the analysis did not reveal any significant differences ($p > 0.05$) by sex or marital status. Overall, based on the results shown in Table 1, Table 3 and the results of independent sample t-test on the attractiveness of flexible work hour arrangement to attract and retain employees, H1 is partially supported.

With regard to whether flexible work hour arrangement has improved the operational efficiency, representatives of the firms unanimously strongly held a view that flexible work hour arrangement had not negatively influenced in achieving project targets (mean = 4.73, SD = 0.45). Further, they expressed that the provision of flexible work hour arrangement had not negatively influenced employees covering the expected number of hours for scheduled periods (mean = 3.98, SD = 0.32).

Study 2: External flexibility

Independent sample t-test was conducted to identify any significant differences in relation to five work outcomes between casual and permanent workers. The results showed significant differences between the two groups with regard to job satisfaction ($p < 0.01$), job

performance ($p < 0.001$), intention to stay ($p < 0.001$), opportunities for skill development ($p < 0.001$) and absenteeism ($p < 0.05$). These significant differences suggest that casual workers reported more negative perceptions compared to permanent workers.

Table 4 shows the results of logistic regression. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 73. Hosmer and Lemeshow test yielded p-value of 0.79. Table 4 suggests that job performance, job satisfaction, absenteeism, intention to stay and opportunities for skill development are important outcomes that differentiate the two groups. The odds of workers in permanent job positions to perceive a higher level of job satisfaction are 1.29 times as high with compared to casual workers. The odds of workers in permanent job positions to perceive a higher level of job performance are 3.19 times as high with compared to casual workers. The odds of workers in permanent job positions to perceive a higher level of intention to stay are 1.32 times as high with compared to casual workers. The odds of workers in permanent job positions to perceive more opportunities for skill development are 11.27 times as high with compared to casual workers. The odds of workers in casual employment arrangement to perceive a higher level of absenteeism intention are 1.15 times as high with compared to permanent workers. Overall, H2 is supported.

Take in Table 4

Study 3: Numerical flexibility

The results of employees' evaluation of shift-work arrangement are shown in Table 5. There were significant differences by marital status for four items, namely, "I get adequate rest time after each shift" ($p < 0.01$), "management provides care and support required for shift-work" ($p < 0.01$), "I can mutually interchange shifts among team members if there is such a requirement" ($p < 0.05$) and "working on a shift system has helped me to find time to continue my higher studies" ($p < 0.05$). Married employees scored higher for all these items with compared to single employees. However, there were no significant differences by age.

Take in Table 5

The results of factor analysis are shown in Table 6. We identified these factors as “learning and growth”, “smooth functioning of job tasks” and “shift-work facilitation”. The analysis of these broad categories did not reveal any significant differences by age or marital status.

Take in Table 6

Table 7 shows the results of logistic regression. For this, the significant items from Table 5 were used. P-value of 0.60 of Hosmer and Lemeshow test suggested a good fit. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 68. It is evident from Table 7 that these four items differentiate employees by marital status. The odds of single employees (as opposed to married) to perceive that management provides care and support required for shift-work are 1.82 times as high. The odds of single employees (as opposed to married) to perceive receiving adequate rest time after each shift are 1.52 times as high. The odds of single employees (as opposed to married) to perceive that working on a shift system has helped to find time to continue higher studies are 0.69 times as high. However, the odds of married employees (as opposed to single) to perceive that they can mutually interchange shifts among team members if there is such a requirement are 0.61 times as high. Overall, H3 is partially supported.

Take in Table 7

Study 4: Functional flexibility

The mean values and zero-order correlations between variables are shown in Table 8. The mean values suggest that employees experience autonomy support, social support and competence support at work (Adj $R^2 = 0.337$; $p < 0.001$).

Take in Table 8

The regression results are shown in Table 9. Data shown in Table 9 support H4 that employees' experience of autonomy support, social support and competence support lead to higher levels of job performance.

Take in Table 9

Conclusion and implications

Economies around the world have become globally interdependent, introducing new forms of relationship between the economy, state and society. Sri Lanka, like other Asian countries, moves towards operating in a global market offering liberal and dynamic business environment; this is expected to bring economic, social and strategic benefits for the country. Sri Lanka is one of the main countries having a well-developed human resource base in Asia, which assist immensely in the government led development initiatives. Changes occurring with the globalization of business operations and increase in operating costs in the West increased the importance of developing countries in the manufacturing and export trade. The four business sectors presented in this paper rely on people for the success. Being labour intensive industries, workforce flexibility suggest a new form of employment arrangement, which could be very much relevant for the business success. The findings presented employees' interpretation of their experience of workforce flexibility strategies, and these findings bring forth both theoretical and practical implications.

With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature, understanding employees' evaluation of their experience of workforce flexibility strategies is important for several reasons. First, organizations increasingly realize the need of operating in a global market and the need of adopting global strategies. Because of such developments, there is a growing research interest in people management in developing countries for survival and growth. During the past two decades interest in workforce flexibility strategies has been growing, and the concept of workforce flexibility is often mentioned as a desirable characteristic of firms and employees. Flexible firms could exhibit increased ability to change in response to changes in product/service market as well as labour market conditions. Still, a firm's ability to adapt to flexibility depends to a large degree on the flexibility exhibited by its employees, which could be indentified through employees' interpretations. Further, each flexibility strategy discussed in the paper has different demands on the flexibility of their

employees. Employees' interpretations provide valuable information on employees themselves, firms and the surrounding society – their adaptation to demands of workforce flexibility strategies. However, the main shortcoming of previous publications lays, on the one hand, that they include a limited number of workforce flexibility strategies in one particular publication. Therefore, it is reasonable to present all the workforce flexibility strategies in a single publication within an extended framework. We have extended the discussion of workforce flexibility by analyzing all four strategies, which are until recently had been presented separately. The firms we studied exclusively cater for export markets. It is vital to provide key information that could enable academics and practitioners to make informed managerial decisions in a global context. All these constitute a major gap in the literature. Analyses in this article address this gap by presenting empirical evidence of employees' interpretations of their experiences of workforce flexibility, interest in which has been growing.

Second, the findings revealed the importance of sex and marital status in shaping individuals interpretations of flexible work hour arrangement and shift-work. It was revealed that in few aspects what is wanted by individuals vary by their sex and marital status. Still, there is a marked absence of research literature on the impact of workforce flexibility strategies on individuals. More research in this area is needed to determine the variables that define reactions to workforce flexibility strategies, thereby allowing suitable updates to be made in order to prevent the deterioration of workplace conditions in organizations.

With regard to the contribution of the study for practice, first, employee attitudes imply that flexible work hour arrangement trigger a variety of changes in the quality of life. It facilitates the reconciliation of work and family needs and allow individuals to balance both responsibilities. Further, employees have not revealed any symptoms where supervisors and colleagues reacting negatively towards those who take benefits of flexible work hour arrangement, they have not had difficulties in interacting with colleagues, and have not had feelings of disconnected from work. Overall, employees showed more positive response towards flexible work hour arrangement. The findings by sex are also important. Investment and trade liberalization of South Asian economies, like in Sri Lanka, have created considerable employment opportunities for those, including women, who possess marketable skills. Although it was assumed that flexible work hour arrangement would be more associated with achieving work-life balance for females than for males, the findings of the study suggested that irrespective of the sex, employees prefer flexible work hour arrangement. Hence, it could be argued that males share equally in family responsibilities in

dual income families. Although results from this study indicate that there are some differences by sex in the attitudes towards flexible work hour arrangement, the majority of differences are not significant. This strengthens the argument that irrespective of the sex, employees prefer flexible work hour arrangement since it addresses their important work-life needs. In this context, the implementation of flexible work hours could be identified as an adoption of more employee friendly strategies for the effective utilization of existing workforce.

Second, in connection to the above, the results imply that flexible work hour arrangement could be adopted as a strategy for the attraction of employees. Therefore, the findings of the study support the offering of flexible work hour arrangement as an inducement to recruitment enhancing a firm's reputation as an employer of choice. It would, however, not be effective in the retention of employees. Therefore, the findings does not provide support for the offering of flexible work hour arrangement as an inducement to retention. Irrespective of sex and marital status respondents held almost similar views in this regard. In this context, the findings suggest that firms have to understand the needs of prospective employees and consider implications of flexible work hour arrangement on recruitment when analyzing costs related to the provision of flexible work hour arrangement.

Third, as an external flexibility strategy, firms make use of external labour through non-standard employment arrangements when necessary, such as casuals. However, research provides evidence that the use of "long-term casuals" engaged in core jobs side-by-side permanent employees can cause people management issues at work. Specifically, casual employees reported low levels of job performance, job satisfaction, absenteeism and opportunities for skill development. Still, firms identify the benefits of "long-term casuals" to reduce non-unionization of workforce and operational costs, and to address temporary labour shortages. However, this trend gives rise to inferior conditions of employment. Gaps in the labour regulatory system have created an environment where unprotected employment arrangements survive and even flourish.

Fourth, as a numerical flexibility strategy, firms make variations of the amount of work by the adoption of shift-work. Firms, especially in the global outsourced IT sector, use shift-work schedules in which employees succeed each other at the same workstation in shifts on some regular basis as directed by the firm. In global off-shore outsourced IT sector, IT professionals located in different parts of the world work collaboratively on the same project. Shift-based work structure allows these firms to synchronize activities of the software development between team members. In this context, IT professionals' evaluation of their

shift-based work structure becomes important as they have to bridge, overcome, routinely cross and even transcend the time and place division to perform their job tasks. The findings highlight the areas that call for improvements in facilitating IT professionals to maximize the benefits of shift-work as well as to minimize the harmful consequences of shift-work on them. Hence, the findings provide useful information for practitioners to guide their actions in creating suitable work environment for shift-workers. Further, findings provide valuable information for policy makers to become familiar with shift-work environment within which employees operate as well as effects of shift-work on employees and firms. Furthermore, the findings provide useful information for shift-workers themselves to become familiar with the consequences of shift-work on them, their families and social lives.

Fifth, as a functional flexibility strategy, firms make changes to the content of work with regard to workers' qualifications by adopting job rotation and horizontal and vertical skill integration. The findings showed that functional flexibility demands support from co-workers as well as supervisors to create a shared sense of responsibility and balance workload between workers in lean production. There is a growing interest in understanding strategies that can be used to make work contexts motivating and increase shop-floor worker involvement. The importance of shop-floor worker adjustment has become vital when firms are adopting advanced manufacturing technologies for survival and growth. In this context, as one of the workforce flexibility strategies, the potential of functional flexibility is promising.

Finally, the platform indeed for any industry is better educated and trained employees; employers expect them to stay longer in a job. Retaining employees as long as possible means keeping them happy in their jobs. The adoption of workforce flexibility strategies means previously uncharted challenges as both parties attempt to create a working relationship that simultaneously recognises and realizes the needs of organizations and employees. Since trade and investment liberalization of Sri Lanka in 1978 governments and private sector propagate strategies to avoid the unionization of workforce. All the sectors we studied in this article are non-unionized. Therefore, workforce flexibility strategies should not be considered as a strategy of its own. Workforce flexibility can be identified as a result of developments in the institutional environment rather than rational decisions made at the firm-level. At the firm-level, a particular firm could adopt all the four strategies simultaneously, making workforce flexibility strategies as a part of the total approach towards its people management. This demands more strategic approach to human resource management. Further, there is a need to continuously monitor its effectiveness and identify needed modifications in its implementation recognizing this as an opportunity. Furthermore,

administration of and adaptation to a new working arrangements- workforce flexibility strategies- may demand training and policy planning in several areas such as communication and team working. Therefore, the role of human resource professionals in the process of adjusting to new realities of the workplace could not be ignored in managing individuals' expectations and experience in the workplace.

Limitations and areas for future research

Each study has its own limitations. Regarding the study on internal flexibility, i.e., flexible work hour arrangement, we investigated organization-led formal flexible work hour arrangements. Future research could look into the effects of flexible work hour arrangement on organizational performance, such as productivity. Regarding the study on external flexibility, i.e., permanent vs casual employment status, it was confined to a single firm. Still, considering the limited number of empirical research on external flexibility and the growing use of non-standard employment arrangements, our study provided important insights for future research. However, there are differences in the meaning associated with the term casual worker across the world. Therefore, future studies could incorporate details of job characteristics of casual workers and how differences in work-related outcomes emerge as a result of differences in work contexts. Regarding the study on numerical flexibility, i.e., shift-work, we have not incorporated shift-work scheduling mechanisms and rewards directed for the effort invested by shift-workers in the job. Therefore, future research could investigate the effect of shift scheduling mechanisms such as how the shifts are rotated and the speed of rotation on employees. Further, future research could incorporate features of reward systems directed for the effort invested by shift-workers in the job. Regarding the study on functional flexibility, i.e., job rotation and horizontal and vertical skill integration, future research could incorporate the characteristics of job tasks performed and the nature of autonomy support provided by supervisors and social support received within the work context to broaden the scope of investigations.

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Tables

Table 1: Employees' evaluation of flexible work hour arrangement

Item	Male Mean (SD)	Female Mean (SD)	<i>t</i> -test
Helps to balance work and family life	4.30 (0.74)	4.57 (0.60)	1.369
Workplace reacts negatively to people using flexible work hour arrangement (R)	4.11 (0.86)	4.47 (0.61)	1.639
Helps to balance work and social life	4.11 (0.86)	4.47 (0.61)	1.601
Leads to miss important workplace events (R)	4.11 (0.93)	4.26 (0.80)	0.587
Feels disconnected from workplace (R)	3.89 (0.78)	4.26 (0.56)	1.841*
Negatively impacts on career progress (R)	3.94 (0.59)	4.05 (0.40)	0.721
Reduces workplace learning opportunities (R)	4.00 (0.68)	3.74 (0.80)	-1.266
Leads to difficulties in interacting with colleagues (R)	3.69 (0.98)	4.26 (0.56)	2.732**
Motivates towards work	3.80 (0.71)	3.78 (0.64)	-0.110
Reduces team spirit (R)	3.86 (0.77)	3.68 (0.67)	-0.821
Enables to focus on job when at workplace	3.71 (0.85)	3.47 (1.02)	-0.919
Feels less restriction at work	3.54 (0.85)	3.78 (0.97)	0.965
Provides time for higher studies	3.08 (0.95)	3.63 (0.83)	2.103*

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; (R) denotes reverse-scored items, where high scores indicate favourable attitudes towards the use of flexible work hour arrangement. SD = standard deviation.

Table 2. Results of factor analysis for employees' evaluation of flexible work hour arrangement

Item	Factors				
	F1: Relations with others at work	F2: Effects on life at work	F3: Balancing work-life	F4: Feeling of freedom	F5: Attention to work
Leads to miss important workplace events (R)	0.705				
Leads to difficulties in interacting with colleagues (R)	0.674				
Feels disconnected from workplace (R)	0.659				
Reduces team spirit (R)	0.645				
Workplace reacts negatively towards those who use flexible work hour arrangement (R)		0.804			
Reduces workplace learning opportunities (R)		0.754			
Negatively impacts on career progress (R)		0.750			
Helps to balance work and family life			0.942		
Helps to balance work and social life			0.839		
Feels less restriction at work				0.841	
Provides time for higher studies				0.705	
Enables to focus on job when at workplace					0.807
Motivates towards work					0.796
Percentage of variance explained	28.15	15.01	10.94	9.35	8.38
Cronbach's Alpha	0.750	0.757	0.835	0.713	0.742

Table 3. Summary of results of logistic regression – flexible work hour arrangement

Item	β	SE	Wald	Exp(B)
Feels disconnected from workplace (R)	0.674	0.390	2.988	0.510*
Leads to difficulties in interacting with colleagues (R)	1.378	0.595	5.355	3.966**
Provides time for higher studies	1.285	0.657	3.829	0.977*

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; SE = standard error

Table 4. Summary of results of logistic regression - external flexibility

Variable	β	SE	Wald	Exp(B)
Job satisfaction	0.280	0.363	0.597	1.289**
Job performance	1.161	0.584	3.995	3.192***
Absenteeism	-0.139	0.412	0.813	1.149*
Intention to stay	0.254	0.234	1.175	1.324***
Opportunities for skill development	2.442	0.981	6.100	11.267***

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 5. Employees' evaluation of shift-work arrangement

Item	Single Mean (SD)	Married Mean (SD)	t-test
I can mutually interchange shifts among team members if there is such a requirement	3.57 (0.96)	3.96 (0.87)	-1.766*
Working on a shift system has opened career development opportunities	3.97 (0.82)	3.67 (0.84)	1.320
Supervisors assist to avoid conflicts when performing job tasks on shift-basis	3.40 (1.10)	3.51 (0.98)	-0.572
Shift-workers have good understanding about their job role	3.47 (0.76)	3.61 (0.83)	-0.988
I get adequate rest time after each shift	3.98 (0.61)	3.59 (0.96)	2.752**
Clear job descriptions are available for shift-workers	3.47 (0.97)	3.32 (0.99)	0.840
Effective procedures are available to handover the work from one shift to another	3.39 (0.83)	3.24 (0.96)	0.937
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to continue my higher studies	3.32 (1.06)	3.07 (1.12)	2.008*
I can get leave from work if there is such a requirement	3.08 (1.09)	2.91 (0.93)	0.939
Management provides care and support required for shift-work	4.10 (.80)	3.64 (.82)	3.158**
Working on a shift system allowed me to get good guidance and assistance from superiors	2.92 (0.95)	2.85 (0.89)	0.308
I get additional financial allowances as a shift-worker	2.84 (1.05)	2.73 (1.04)	0.583
Working on a shift system has opened new career opportunity for me	2.71 (0.94)	2.61 (1.08)	0.505

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

Table 6. Results of factor analysis for employees' evaluation of shift-work arrangement

Item	F1: Learning and growth	F2: Smooth functioning of job tasks	F3: Shift- work facilitation
Working on a shift system has opened new career opportunity for me	0.794		
Working on a shift system has opened career development opportunities	0.762		
Working on a shift system allowed me to get good guidance and assistance from superiors	0.757		
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to continue my higher studies	0.743		
Clear job descriptions are available for shift-workers		0.788	
Supervisors assist to avoid conflicts when performing job tasks on shift-basis		0.725	
Shift-workers have good understanding about their job role		0.722	
Effective procedures are available to handover the work from one shift to another		0.712	
I get additional financial allowances as a shift-worker			0.790
I can get leave from work if there is such a requirement			0.788
I get adequate rest time after each shift			0.776
I can mutually interchange shifts among team members if there is such a requirement			0.759
Management provides care and support required for shift-work			0.743
Percentage of variance explained	28.18	20.72	14.19
Cronbach's Alpha	0.768	0.725	0.779

Table 7. Summary of results of logistic regression - numerical flexibility

Item	β	SE	Wald	Exp(B)
I can mutually interchange shifts among team members if there is such a requirement	-0.378	0.197	3.692	0.609*
Working on a shift system has helped me to find time to continue my higher studies	0.496	0.252	3.870	0.685*
Management provides care and support required for shift-work	2.599	0.230	6.765	1.820**
I get adequate rest time after each shift	1.664	0.261	6.478	1.515**

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

Table 8. Correlations

	Mean	SD	1	2	3
1. Autonomy support	3.78	0.77	1		
2. Competence support	4.09	0.66	0.579**	1	
3. Social support	4.05	0.68	0.456**	0.559**	1
4. Job performance	3.98	0.59	0.432**	0.518**	0.488**

** $p < 0.01$

Table 9. Summary of results of regression analysis – functional flexibility

Variable	β	Adj R^2	F
Autonomy support	0.148***	0.337	114.17***
Competence support	0.286***		
Social support	0.261***		

*** $p < 0.001$